

Mathematical Representation of Logical and Computational Operations

Abstract:

This paper presents a mathematical framework for representing logical and computational operations using a set of equations based on elementary mathematical concepts. The framework includes equations for comparisons, boolean logic, arithmetic operations, and conversions between binary and decimal representations. These equations provide a versatile means of representing complex computational processes as mathematical expressions, allowing for a deeper understanding of the underlying logic and functionality.

1. Introduction

Mathematical representations of logical and computational operations are valuable tools for understanding and analyzing algorithms and programs. This paper introduces a set of equations that can be used to represent various logical and computational operations, including comparisons, boolean logic, arithmetic operations, and binary-to-decimal conversions.

2. Comparison Equations

2.1 Less and Equal Equation

$$le(a,b) = \lfloor 1 - \frac{(a-b)}{(|a-b|+1)} \rfloor$$

Returns 1 when $a \leq b$ and 0 when $b > a$.

This is true because if a is less than b then $a-b$ is a negative, meaning the division will return a negative fraction. When 1 is subtracted by this fraction, the equation will return a decimal that is greater than 1. Rounding down returns 1. Otherwise the fraction from the division is simply subtracted by 1 and is less than 1, floored to return 0. When a and b are equal it acts as $1 - 0/1$ which is the same as $1 - 0$, and that equals 1.

2.2 More and Equal Equation

$$me(a,b) = \lfloor 1 - \frac{(b-a)}{(|b-a|+1)} \rfloor$$

Returns 0 when $a < b$ and 1 when $b \geq a$.

This inverts the less and equal equation, so that B acts like A and A acts like B

2.3 Equal Equation

$$e(a,b) = (\lfloor 1 - \frac{(a-b)}{(|a-b|+1)} \rfloor + \lfloor 1 - \frac{(b-a)}{(|b-a|+1)} \rfloor) - 1$$

Returns 1 when $a = b$ and 0 otherwise.

This adds results of the less/equal and more/equal equations with a and b together so that when $a = b$ the addition returns 2, subtracting 1 making the equation return 1, otherwise the addition returns 1 and the subtraction will return 0.

2.4 More Equation

$$m(a,b) = (L \ 1 - ((b-a)/(|b-a|+1)) \ J) - ((L \ 1 - ((a-b)/(|a-b|+1)) \ J) + L \ 1 - ((b-a)/(|b-a|+1)) \ J) - 1)$$

Returns 1 when $a > b$ and 0 otherwise.

This equation works by subtracting the equal equation from the more equal equation, so that when both the more equal and equal equations return 1 then this equation returns 0. This only returns 0 and 1 because the equal equation will never be true when the more equation is not true.

2.5 Less Equation

$$l(a,b) = (L \ 1 - ((a-b)/(|a-b|+1)) \ J) - ((L \ 1 - ((a-b)/(|a-b|+1)) \ J) + L \ 1 - ((b-a)/(|b-a|+1)) \ J) - 1)$$

Returns 1 when $a < b$ and 0 otherwise.

This acts the same ways as the More equation, the only difference being that it is the equal equation subtracted by the less equal equation

2.6 Not Equal Equation

$$ne(a,b) = |((L \ 1 - ((a-b)/(|a-b|+1)) \ J) + L \ 1 - ((b-a)/(|b-a|+1)) \ J) - 1| - 1|$$

Returns 1 when $a \neq b$ and 0 when $a = b$.

This equation takes the equal equation and will subtract 1 and get the absolute value, so that if the equal equation were to return 0 then that subtraction makes it -1 which abs is 1, and if the equal equation were to return 1 then that subtraction makes it 0. This idea of subtracting 1 and getting the absolute value works for any of the provided equations that return 0 or 1 to get its inverse.

2.6.1 Base Inverse:

$$\text{Inverse}(\text{equation}) = |\text{equation}-1|$$

This works for any equation that returns 0 or 1 because when the equation returns 0 then subtracting 1 returns -1 and the absolute value of -1 is 1, otherwise it will return 0

3. Logical and Computational Operations

3.1 Base controlled output:

It is possible to allow for any output to be outputted for a equation that returns 0 or 1 by multiplying the value you want returned when the equation is found to be true by the equation, and adding the result to the result of multiplying the output you want returned when the equation is false by the inverse of the equation.

$$\text{BaseReturn}(\text{equation}, t, f) = t * \text{equation} + f * \text{inverse}(\text{equation})$$

This works because of the fact that if the base equation were to return 0 then multiplying by the truth value will only return 0, but the inverse of the equation will have returned 1 so multiplying that inverse by the false value will return the false value. This means that the equation will only ever return the truth or the false value but never their sum.

3.2 IF Equation

$$\text{IF}(a, b, t, f, c, d) = (((((((t * ((L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - 1)) + (f * ((L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - 1)))J + L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((d - 0) / (|d - 0| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((0 - d) / (|0 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((d - 0) / (|d - 0| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((0 - d) / (|0 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * (((f * ((L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - 1)) + (t * ((L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((d - 1) / (|d - 1| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((1 - d) / (|1 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((d - 1) / (|d - 1| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((1 - d) / (|1 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((c - 1) / (|c - 1| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((1 - c) / (|1 - c| + 1)))J) - 1) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((c - 1) / (|c - 1| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((1 - c) / (|1 - c| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) + (((((((t * (L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) + (f * ((L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((d - 0) / (|d - 0| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((0 - d) / (|0 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((d - 0) / (|d - 0| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((0 - d) / (|0 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * (((t * ((L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - (L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((d - 1) / (|d - 1| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((1 - d) / (|1 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((d - 1) / (|d - 1| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((1 - d) / (|1 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((c - 2) / (|c - 2| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((2 - c) / (|2 - c| + 1)))J) - 1) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((c - 2) / (|c - 2| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((2 - c) / (|2 - c| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) + (((((((t * (L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J) + (f * ((L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((d - 0) / (|d - 0| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((0 - d) / (|0 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((d - 0) / (|d - 0| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((0 - d) / (|0 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * (((t * ((L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J) - (L(1 - ((a - b) / (|a - b| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((b - a) / (|b - a| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((d - 1) / (|d - 1| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((1 - d) / (|1 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((d - 1) / (|d - 1| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((1 - d) / (|1 - d| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1))) * ((L(1 - ((c - 3) / (|c - 3| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((3 - c) / (|3 - c| + 1)))J) - 1) + (0 * ((L(1 - ((c - 3) / (|c - 3| + 1)))J + L(1 - ((3 - c) / (|3 - c| + 1)))J) - 1) - 1)))$$

This equation takes the variable c and if it is 1 then equal and not equal equations will be decided upon by d, if 0 then equal, if 1 then not equal, if c is 2 then more equal and more will be decided upon by d, if c is 3 then less equal and less will be decided upon by d. If c is any other value it returns 0 and if d is not 0 or 1 it returns 0. They do not interfere because the part deciding which equation to use returns 0 if that equation is not selected, and everything is added together, so the result will only be the result of a and b per the equation that was chosen.

3.2 Piecewise function

A piecewise function is a function that is defined on a sequence of intervals, so the value changes based on a set of operations, these intervals can be defined with a if statement, with the first interval taking precedent, and then if that one is false then to check the next, and then the next, and then to return a given value, for instance

$$f(x) = \{x < 10: 5, x > 10: 2, 4\}$$

Can be defined as:

$$f(x) = \text{IF}(x, 10, 5, (\text{IF}(x, 10, 2, (4), 2, 1)), 3, 1)$$

While it would be very challenging to actually write out the full extent of the equation, this would return the same graph and result for a given x value as the piecewise function, and it is shown that the IF equation is a singular equation that uses only basic math concepts. The IF equation as well can be simplified down to the individual operations, and simply acts as a general use equation.

3.3 Boolean Logic Equations

Various boolean logic operations, including AND, NAND, OR, NOR, XOR, and XNOR, can be represented using IF equations. These equations provide a mathematical representation of logical operations based on the values of a and b. This is under the assumption that a and b are only ever 1 or 0, otherwise the equations will always return 0.

$$\text{And}(a,b) = \text{IF}(a, 1, \text{IF}(b, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0), 0, 1, 0)$$

$$\text{Nand}(a,b) = |\text{IF}(a, 1, \text{IF}(b, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0), 0, 1, 0) - 1|$$

$$\text{Or}(a,b) = \text{IF}(a, 1, 1, \text{IF}(b, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0), 1, 0)$$

$$\text{Nor}(a,b) = |\text{IF}(a, 1, 1, \text{IF}(b, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0), 1, 0) - 1|$$

$$\text{Xor}(a,b) = \text{IF}(\text{IF}(a, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0) + \text{IF}(b, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0), 1, 1, 0, 1, 0)$$

$$\text{Xnor}(a,b) = |\text{IF}(\text{IF}(a, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0) + \text{IF}(b, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0), 1, 1, 0, 1, 0) - 1|$$

4. Arithmetic Operations

4.1 Integer Division

$\text{intdiv}(a, b) = \text{IF}(a/b, 0, \lfloor a/b \rfloor, \lceil a/b \rceil, 2, 0)$

Represents integer division of a by b.

4.2 Modulo Operation

$\text{mod}(\text{dev}, \text{div}) = \text{IF}(\text{div}, 0, (\text{dev} - \text{IF}(\text{dev}/\text{div}, 0, \lfloor \text{dev}/\text{div} \rfloor, \lceil \text{dev}/\text{div} \rceil, 2, 0)) * \text{div}), -1, 1, 1)$

Calculates the modulo of dev with respect to div without using loops.

4.3 Get Digit

$\text{getDigit}(N, l) = \text{mod}(\text{intdiv}(N, 10^l), 10)$

Returns the digit at index l in the number N.

4.4 Binary-to-Decimal Conversion

4.4.1 BinaryToDecimal

$\text{BTD}(a, l) = \text{IF}(l, 1, \text{getDigit}(a, l) * 2^l + \text{BTD}(a, l-1), \text{getDigit}(a, l) * 2^l, 2, 0)$

Converts a binary number a to decimal.

4.4.1.1 Single BinaryToDecimal

$\text{SBTD}(a) = \text{BTD}(a, \lfloor \log(a) \rfloor + 1)$

Converts a binary number a to decimal using the length of a.

4.4.2.1 DecimalToBinary

$\text{DTB}(N, a, i) = \text{IF}(i, 0, \text{DTB}(N - 2^i, (a + \text{IF}(2^i, N, 1, 0, 3, 1)) * 10, i-1), a, 2, 0)$

Converts a decimal number N to binary, with a representing the binary result and i as the index of the current binary digit.

4.4.2.2 Single DecimalToBinary

$\text{SDTB}(N) = \text{DTB}(N, 0, \lceil \log_2(N) \rceil)$

Converts a decimal number N to binary using the length of N.

7. Conclusion

This paper has presented a mathematical framework for representing logical and computational operations using a set of equations based on elementary mathematical concepts. These equations can be used to represent a wide range of operations and provide a deeper understanding of the underlying logic and functionality of algorithms and programs. Theoretically any functional program could be broken down into a mathematical equation, as well as most complicated mathematical components, assuming that all inputs and outputs are broken down into numbers, and all exterior interactions within the program are either removed or otherwise accounted for. The mathematical equations themselves are relatively easy to understand the functionality, even when it is not obvious, so it could be used as a learning tool for explaining a different way in which these mathematical equations work. It should be noted that the If function is used, but that is a selector function that allows for the other values to be checked, so a majority of the formula in the function is not used, and instead only that part that returns a value that is not 0